

Polarographic Studies on Electrode Kinetics and Formation Constants of the Complexes Formed by In(III) and Eu(III) with Quinolate Ions

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The reduction of In(III) and Eu(III) in NaClO₄ ($\mu=1.5$) at d.m.e. is found to be quasireversible, but it becomes reversible in the presence of quinolate ions in case of Eu(III). The $E_{1/2}^r$ values for the simple Eu(III) ion and for In(III)-Quinolate system are calculated from the observed $E_{1/2}$ values by Gelling's treatment and from it the kinetic parameters have been calculated. The formation constants have been calculated by DeFord and Hume method. In both systems four complex species are formed. In(III) forms stronger complex species as compared to Eu(III). The percentage distribution of the various species present in both the systems is calculated.

In(III) and Eu(III) form complexes with a number of ligands but the reduction are not reversible at d.m.e. and hence the formation constants could not be calculated from observed half-wave potentials. With the development of Koryta's¹, Matsuda's² and Gelling's³ methods for quasireversible reduction, the reversible half-wave potentials ($E_{1/2}^r$) can be obtained from the C-V curves and thus the formation constants can be calculated.

By applying foregoing methods, the polarographic studies of the complexes formed by Eu(III) with CDTA have been carried out by Jain and Gaur⁴ and with some aromatic substituted acids by Anand Kumar⁵. Recently, Eu(III) complexes with crotonate, itaconate, citraconate, 6 amino hexanoate, gluconate and 2 furoate ions have been polarographically studied by the authors^{6,7}.

In(III) forms complexes with various ligands; six thiocyanate complex species of In(III) have been reported⁸. Polarographic studies on the electrode kinetics and formation constants of the complexes formed by In(III) with 1 : 2 Diaminocyclohexanetetraacetic acid (CDTA)⁹ and with aspirin¹⁰ have been carried out. Recently the electrochemical behaviour of In(III) complexes with crotonate ion and gluconate¹¹ ions at DME has been investigated. The authors have reported¹² In(III) complexes with α -picolinic acid also.

The present paper deals with the determination of kinetic parameters and formation constants of the complexes of Eu(III) and In(III) with quinolate ions.

Experimental

A manual polarographic set up was used for obtaining C-V curves. The DME having the characteristics $m=1.7645$ mgm/sec. and $t=3.64$ sec. (open circuit) was used. Sodium salt of quinolinic acid was used as the complexing agent. The polarograms were recorded after deaeration (20-25 minutes) with nitrogen. All the measurements were carried out at $30\pm 0.1^\circ$ maintained by a Haaketype ultra-thermostat. Solution containing 0.5 mM Eu(III) and In(III) and different amounts of complexing agents were prepared. The ionic strength was kept at 1.5 by adding the requisite amount of sodium perchlorate solution. An H-type cell with an agar-agar plug saturated with sodium chloride served as electrolytic cell.

Results and Discussion

A single well-defined reduction wave appeared in each case. Plots of i_d vs \sqrt{h} and i_d vs metal ions-concentration were straight lines passing through the origin, showing that the reductions are controlled by diffusion. The half-wave potentials shifted to more negative values and i_d was found to decrease with increasing concentration of the ligand indicating complex formation.

In(III)-Quinolate system †

The plots of $\log i/i_d - i$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ were linear but slopes come to be of the order of 25 ± 1 mV, which is higher than the required for three electron reduction. Therefore, the reversible half-wave potentials were determined by modified Gelling's

method^{8,13} from the observed $E_{1/2}$ values by plotting $\left[E - \frac{RT}{nF} \log \frac{i_0-i}{i} \right]$ vs 'i' and by extrapolating $i=0$ (Fig.1). The standard rate constant, K_s , and transfer coefficient, α , have been calculated from the plots of $\log (z-1)$ vs $(E - E_{1/2}^r)$, which results to straight line (Fig. 2). The value of K_s was found to be of the order of 10^{-4} cm/sec. which confirms that the electrode process is quasi-reversible in all cases.

The $E_{1/2}^r$ vs $-\log C_X$ plots were smooth curves in all cases showing the existence of two or more complexes in equilibria. The overall stability constants were calculated by the DeFord and Hume^{14,15} treatment. The details of the method have been explained in an earlier paper¹⁶.

Fig. 1. Plots of i vs $\left[E - \frac{RT}{nF} \log \frac{i_0-i}{i} \right]$ For In(III)-Quinolate system

The plots of $F_j [X]$ vs C_X to zero ligand concentration (Fig.3) showed the presence of four complex species: $[In(quinolate)]^+$, $[In(quinolate)_2]^-$, $[In(quinolate)_3]^{-2}$ and $[In(quinolate)_4]^{-3}$ with $\beta_1=3 \times 10^6$, $\beta_2=4 \times 10^7$, $\beta_3=33 \times 10^7$ and $\beta_4=100 \times 10^7$ respectively. The polarographic characteristics, $F_0([X])$ functions and kinetic parameters have been summarised in Table 1. The percentage distribution of In(III) in various forms has been shown in Fig.4.

Eu(III) Quinolate system :

Again the plots of $\log i/i_0-i$ vs $E_{1/2}$ were found to be linear, but the slope for simple metal ion was 90mV, whereas the value reduces to 60 ± 2 mV in presence of quinolate ion. Thus the electrode reaction is not reversible in case of simple metal ion

Fig. 2. Plots of $\log (z-1)$ vs $(E_{1/2}^r - E)$ For In(III)-Quinolate system

Fig. 3. Plots of $F_j([X])$ vs C_X For In(III)-Quinolate system

Fig. 4. Plots of % distribution vs $-\log C_X$ For In(III)-Quinolate system

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS, FO ([X]) SUNCTIONS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR IN(III) QUINOLINATE SYSTEM

C_X (Moles)	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (-V vs SCE)	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}^r$	i_d (μ .A.)	$F_0(X)$ $\times 10^{-7}$	α	λ (sec.^{-1})	$D^{\frac{1}{2}} \times 10^3$ ($\text{cm}^2/\text{sec.}$)	$K_s \times 10^3$ ($\text{cm}/\text{sec.}$)
0.00	0.5250	0.622	7.598	—	0.334	1.788	4.60	8.227
0.05	0.6855	0.686	7.462	0.030	0.375	1.357	4.53	6.146
0.10	0.7070	0.704	7.416	0.119	0.394	1.558	4.50	7.000
0.15	0.7190	0.716	7.416	0.312	0.474	1.488	4.50	7.000
0.20	0.7280	0.726	7.402	0.642	0.592	2.357	4.52	10.655
0.25	0.7355	0.734	7.402	1.234	0.524	2.645	4.52	11.955
0.30	0.7425	0.741	7.280	2.164	0.592	2.357	4.42	10.419
0.35	0.7480	0.747	7.180	3.518	0.575	2.706	4.30	11.553

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND F_j ([X]) VALUES FOR EU(III)-QUINOLINATE SYSTEM AT 30°C ($\mu=1.5$)

C_X (Moles)	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (-V vs SCE)	i_d (Divs.)	F_0 ([X]) $\times 10^{-5}$	F_1 ([X]) $\times 10^{-3}$	F_2 ([X]) $\times 10^{-4}$	F_3 ([X]) $\times 10^{-4}$	F_4 ([X]) $\times 10^{-4}$
0.00	0.6635*	93.0	—	—	—	—	—
0.05	0.7500	85.0	0.507	10.134	16.63	—	—
0.10	0.8055	82.0	4.429	44.290	42.29	—	—
0.15	0.8420	80.5	18.300	122.000	80.00	266.67	944.47
0.20	0.8655	80.0	40.820	204.100	101.05	305.25	900.00
0.25	0.8800	80.0	79.200	316.800	125.92	343.68	874.72
0.30	0.8960	80.0	146.300	487.670	168.89	406.30	937.67
0.35	0.9080	79.0	234.800	670.860	191.10	431.71	876.30

* $E_{\frac{1}{2}} - E_{r_{\frac{1}{2}}}$

but it becomes reversible by the addition of quinolate ions. This has been confirmed by Gelling's method as shown in Fig. 5.

The kinetic parameters for the simple metal ion Eu(III) in 1.5 M NaClO₄ were calculated. The diffusion coefficient for Eu(III) comes to 5.43x10⁻⁶ cm²/sec. The value of K_s and α come to 2.67x10⁻⁴ cm/sec. and 0.81 respectively, confirming the quasi-reversible nature of the electrode process in the absence of ligand.

The plot of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ vs -log C_X was found to be straight line, showing the formation of two or more complex species. The plots of F_j ([X]) vs C_X to

zero ligand concentration showed the presence of four complexes : [Eu(quinolate)]⁺, [Eu(quinolate)₂]⁻, [Eu(quinolate)₃]⁻² and [Eu(quinolate)₄]⁻³ with β₁=2x10³, β₂=40x10⁴, β₃=125x10⁴ and β₄=900 x 10⁴ respectively. The polarographic characteristics and F_j ([X]) values have been included in Table 2. The distribution of Eu(III) in its various forms is presented in Fig. 6.

It is evident that the complexes of quinolate ion with In(III) are much stronger than those with Eu(III). Since all the reductions are found to be diffusion controlled, Eu(III) and In(III) can be estimated polarographically in the persence of quinolate ions.

Fig. 5. Plots of i vs $\left[E - \frac{RT}{nF} \log \frac{id-i}{i} \right]$ For Eu(III)—Quinolate system

Fig. 6. Plots of % distribution vs -log C_x For Eu(III)—Quinolate system

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